

Monumentality, Seriality and Social Intervention: Stone Sculptures from an 11th-Century Workshop at Sunari in Eastern Malwa

Résumé

Cet article porte sur un groupe de sculptures hindoues en pierre provenant de Sunari, au Madhya Pradesh, qui atteste l'existence d'un atelier de sculpteurs local au XI^e siècle. La proximité de ces sculptures avec la ville d'Udaypur et son temple royal apporte de précieuses informations quant à la nature de l'activité artistique dans des localités encore peu connues, restées dans l'ombre de grands centres urbains. Monumentalité et sérialité se révèlent être des clés de compréhension de la production de tels ateliers dans leur capacité à créer une cohérence régionale à partir de traits stylistiques locaux, et à agir sur le tissu social de l'arrière-pays.

Mots-clés : atelier, style, Malwa, dynastie Paramara, XI^e siècle.

概要

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Abstract

This article draws attention to a hitherto unnoticed group of Hindu sculptures from Sunari in Madhya Pradesh, which attests to the existence of a local workshop active during the 11th century. Their proximity to the great temple town of Udaypur affords valuable insights into the nature of artistic activity at little-known locales long overshadowed by major urban centres. Monumentality and seriality emerge as key ideas for understanding the oeuvre of such workshops, both in its capacity to create local distinction and regional coherence, and in its ability to intervene in the social fabric of the hinterland.

Keywords: workshop, style, Malwa, Paramara dynasty, eleventh century.

要約

本論は、十一世紀、マディア・プラデーシュのスナリに由来するヒンドゥーの石刻作品の一群が示す、地域的な彫刻の工房について論じるものである。これらの彫刻作品とウダイプル町、およびその王室神殿の近さは、都市的な大きな中心地の陰に隠れて、まだほとんど知られていない地方で行なわれた芸術活動の性質について、貴重な情報をもたらすものである。これらの工房の作品は、記念碑性とシリーズ性という特徴を示している。こうした特徴を理解することで、この工房の機能の様相と、それが地域文化の一貫性の中でどんな創造性を発揮していたかということ、また都市部周辺地域社会にどのようなダイナミックな社会的インパクトを与える可能性を持っていたかを認識できる。

キーワード： 工房、様式、マラワ、パラマ朝、十一世紀。

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In recent decades, a remarkable group of stone sculptures has come to light from Sunari, located in the Vidisha district of Madhya Pradesh in central India (**map 1**).¹ Over a number of dry seasons between 1993 and 2015, the inhabitants of the village dug out several well-preserved statues from the rocky riverbed adjoining an island in the river Keotan, which flows 1 kilometre to the east of Sunari (**map 2**). Many of these exquisite figural images, carved from the same reddish-beige sandstone, were removed by the state archaeology department in 2006 for display at the district museum in Vidisha (**fig. 1**). Others continue to be safeguarded by the local community within an old *gaḍhī* or castle at Sunari (**fig. 2**).² Some of the largest freestanding sculptures are still in the village, sheltered under a tree on a *cabūtrā*, an old open-air platform shrine situated along the main road next to the earthen embankment of a water reservoir, where they are placed in worship together with various carved fragments that had been lying there previously (**fig. 3**). In contrast to the weathered vestiges from the village, many sculptures from the adjoining riverbed are intact and still exude an extraordinary richness in their stone carving.

Sunari was first explored in 1923–1924 by M.B. Garde, superintending archaeologist of the former Gwalior State, who reported that “near the village, by the side of the cart track leading from Udaypur to Basoda are the bare remains of a shrine, in which are sheltered two badly mutilated sculptures.”³ One of these, the statue of Vishnu seated in meditation as “master of yoga,” Yoganarayana, was brought to Gwalior where it is still on display at the state museum (**fig. 4**).⁴ The other sculpture, probably too damaged to merit removal, may be the headless statue of Shiva-Parvati displayed at the *gaḍhī*’s entrance.⁵ Besides this brief notice, the site has not attracted any attention for nearly a century, nor does it find any mention in the extensive village-to-village survey conducted by the state archaeology department of Madhya Pradesh in the 1990s.⁶ The neglect is particularly surprising given that Sunari is barely 3.5 kilometres southwest of Udaypur (**map 3**), where the famous Udayeshwar temple, founded in 1080 CE (1137 *vikrama*) under the Paramara king Udayaditya, has been the object of sustained art historical

interest since the 19th century.⁷ Unlike Udaypur, Sunari boasts of no monumental architecture nor any significant inscriptions and, thus, has not merited state or scholarly attention.

Among countless such places in the hinterland of major temple towns throughout the vast region of Malwa that await proper exploration (**map 4**), Sunari is of special significance because its sculptures hold important insights into larger questions of monumentality and seriality in workshop production at a time of unprecedented temple-building activity in mediaeval India.

Map 1. — The location of Sunari in Vidisha district, Madhya Pradesh, India. Map: Saarthak Singh.

Map 2. — Sunari and its environs. Map: Saarthak Singh.

1. The village is located at 23°53'31.5"N, 78°01'24.0"E. See Survey of India map 1:50000, sheet no. 551/1 (1976).

Note on diacritics: To facilitate readability, all proper names—including names of historical figures, cultural regions, and religious groups—have been rendered without diacritical marks. Only for specific terms and direct quotations are diacritics used, following the IAST scheme.

2. This has received some coverage in local Hindi newspapers, see SINGH V. 2017.

3. GARDE 1924, p. 8.

4. Gujari Mahal Museum, Gwalior, no. 142. The accession recorded in GARDE 1924, p. 34, no. 46 is erroneously identified as “A Sculpture of Buddha-Avatarā,” later rectified in DIKSHIT 1962, p. 46 and CHAKRAVARTY 1984, p. 65.

5. This is assuming GARDE 1924, p. 8 also misidentified this sculpture, which he calls “Lakshmi-Narayana.”

6. RAG 2007, p. 122, no. 153, lists Sunari among villages where no archaeological remains were found.

7. BEGLAR 1878, pp. 81–88; CUNNINGHAM 1880, pp. 65–69; LASCARIDES-ZANNAS 1981; MEISTER 1983; DWIVEDI 1991, pp. 97–98; TICHIT 2010, 2012, 2014; and PANDE 2018.

^ Map 3. — Sunari and neighbouring sites in the hinterland of Udaypur. Map: Saarthak Singh.

Figure 1. — Vishnu statues, 11th century, Sunari. Sandstone, H. between 130–150 cm. Vidisha District Museum, nos. 1909, 1910, 1916. Photos: Johan Levillain.

Figure 2. — Sculptures displayed in the old castle (*gaḍhī*) of Sunari. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

Figure 3. — Sculptures on the open-air platform shrine (*cabūtrā*) in Sunari. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

Figure 5. — “Varaha no. 1,” 11th century, Sunari. Sandstone, H. 133 cm; L. 147 cm; W. 59.7 cm. Vidisha District Museum, inventory number unavailable. Photo: Johan Levillain.

Figure 6. — “Varaha no. 2,” 11th century, Sunari, in worship at the village. Sandstone, H. 136 cm; L. 134 cm; W. 53 cm. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

Making sense of the prolific artistic production at Sunari—attested by a corpus of more than 40 sculptures, both intact and fragmentary—presents a methodological challenge in the absence of any documentary sources and scholarly research in comparable contexts. Nevertheless, taking the sculptures themselves as sources for their own manufacture can reveal valuable information about the nature of artistic practice. Such analysis necessarily relies on seriation as a method for situating images in a chronological sequence and for identifying patterns and variations based on a range of attributes, including size, format, proportions, iconography, composition, and stylistic treatment. In large part, however, art historians rely on the visual analysis of style, discernible in the consistency and repetition of certain forms that are assumed to circulate within a given geographical range or political formation.¹³ A valuable framework to analyse change and continuity through stylistic analysis was put forth by Michael Meister, who distinguished “style” as a broad set of aggregate conventions changing with political patronage, from “idiom,” a localised tradition enduring with a site and guild of craftsmen.¹⁴ The stakes, as clarified by Ajay Sinha, lie in identifying the innovation, experimentation and individuality integral to any artistic practice, and determining how that contributes to the overall coherence and standardisation of a paradigm in a region or dynastic domain.¹⁵ From this perspective, the Sunari sculptures can be understood as products of creative processes, which, on the one hand, lent distinction to a specific local idiom, and, on the other, ensured their conformity with the broader stylistic consensus in a given region.

Assessing artistic activity at a single site within its broader context also raises questions concerning the social reality that shaped, and was shaped by, sculptural production. One indication that Sunari’s sculptural output may have been spurred by the stability and ideological impetus introduced by dominant political and religious forces is its proximity to Udaypur, which rose into a major urban centre with the foundation of a new town, temple, tank and other works in 1080 CE (*vikrama* 1137), all dedicated to the god Shiva and named after the reigning king of the Paramara dynasty of Malwa (972–1305 CE).¹⁶ No dynastic inscriptions have been found at Sunari so far, but the visible impact of dynastic patronage to Shaivism is attested here by a Shiva-linga and its accompanying pedestal, which are identical in their material and form to the lingas installed at the royal temples of Bhojpur around 1050 and of Udaypur in 1080 (see **fig. 3**).¹⁷ Like their imperial counterparts, they

are made of a distinctive purple sandstone (unlike the other sculptures at Sunari) and have a moulded pedestal to support the square base and octagonal transition of the circular shaft, which is engraved with the aniconic emblem of Shiva. This accords remarkably well with the textual evidence marshalled by Alexis Sanderson for the “rise and dominance of Śaivism” in all spheres of mediaeval society due to its exceptional appeal to royal patrons.¹⁸ Yet, the abundance of Vishnu statues at Sunari during the same period suggests there was substantial space for non-Shaiva devotion in what has been hailed as the “Śaiva Age,” a narrative that must be nuanced through attention to such sources and contexts. Likewise, the role of dynastic patronage appears considerably more complex, for the stylistic affiliations of the statues extend beyond the Paramara domains into the Chandella kingdom, which centred on Khajuraho in neighbouring Bundelkhand (Jejākadeśa) but briefly extended into the Vidisha area (Daśārṇadeśa) during the mid-10th century and again in the early 12th century.¹⁹

Seen on their own terms, however, the devotional statues were not just passive witnesses to changing social conditions, but played a more active role in mediating social affairs, based on their ability to address and affect their audiences in transformative ways. Scholars have found a range of rationales in religious meaning, political ideology or cultural taste to explain the purposiveness of such images. But by locating the capacity for social intervention in the sculptures themselves, we wish to emphasise the dynamic ways in which such meanings and attitudes operated, acted upon and intervened in local contexts through the specific formal qualities of sculpture. Carved in sandstone, on a large scale, with increasing complexity and technical perfection, Sunari’s freestanding figural statuary would have been an extraordinary fixture in its built environment, especially where there is little contemporaneous evidence of monumental stone buildings. Neighbouring villages present a more fragmentary pattern of survival, but the vestiges of figural statuary gathered in modern shrines suggest that there were significant sculptural installations in such little-known locales throughout the countryside (**map 3**). Notably, many of these sites exhibit a qualitative and quantitative surge in their sculptural remains corresponding to the 11th–12th centuries,²⁰ pointing to broader shifts in sculptural production that must have had important implications for this social milieu.

The three interconnected themes encapsulated in the title of our paper are elaborated through a focused analysis of select sculptures from Sunari, interpreting their form, iconography,

13. FLOOD 2015, p. 151.

14. MEISTER 1982, p. 169 and MEISTER 1993, p. 351.

15. SINHA 2000, p. 125.

16. As noted in the Udayeshwar foundation record, see MITTAL 1979, pp. 129–130; TRIVEDI H.V. 1989, p. 612; and SINGH S. 2019.

17. For Bhojpur, see HARDY 2015, pp. 32–33, and AIIS negative no. 28.10, and for Udaypur, PANDE 2018, pp. 85–86, plate 125.

18. SANDERSON 2009, pp. 252–254.

19. See WILLIS 1988, pp. 275–277 for the historical geography of these regions.

20. The sculptural remains at these sites are listed with approximate dates in the village-to-village surveys conducted by the Madhya Pradesh state archaeological department in the 1990s; see RAG 2007, pp. 57–119 for villages of the Ganj Basoda tehsil illustrated in map 3.

Figure 7a. — Vishnu statue enshrined in the Javari temple at Khajuraho (ca. 1075–1100). Photo: Johan Levillain.

Figure 7b. — Vishnu statue, 11th century, Sunari. Sandstone, H. between 130–150 cm. In storage at Sunari. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

Figure 7c. — Composition of a Vishnu statue at Sunari: 1. Vishnu; 2–3. Ayudhapurusha; 4. Garuda; 5. Lakshmi; 6. Parashurama; 7. Rama; 8. Varaha; 9. Narasimha; 10. Vamana; 11. Balarama; 12. Matsya; 13. Kurma; 14. Vishnu; 15. Prithivi; 16. Brahma; 17. Shiva; 18. Buddha; 19. Kalkin. Drawing: Johan Levillain.

style, and chronology, in relation to broader regional and local contexts. We make the case that monumentality and seriality were crucial dimensions of workshop production at this time, not only in terms of the creative processes but also as regards the operative reality of sculpture in the hinterland of major urban centres.

Monumentality and modular production in freestanding temple statuary

Ten of the best-preserved statues of Vishnu studied here all present the god in monumental form at the centre of an elaborate micro-architectural composition, as the paramount god of a cosmic hierarchy (fig. 7). As if emerging from the sanctuary of a temple, the protagonist stands against an openwork background and is framed by subsidiary figures arranged in distinct registers following the format of a shrine doorway. Like the threshold of a sanctuary, the plinth of the statue has a stepped plan whose main projection displays the chthonic and worldly supports of Vishnu's feet: the snake-hooded Earth goddess flanked by two nagas and a pair of kneeling devotees. The uprights of the statue carry forth the triadic rhythm of the plinth projections and emulate the door-jambs of a shrine with their horizontal

divisions and moulded capitals. Leading us through the middle regions of Vishnu's universe are his door-guardians stationed in serried ranks to the right and left: the personified weapons conch and discus, followed by his mount Garuda and consort Lakshmi, and finally his martial avatars Parashurama and Rama. The sequence of avatars continues at diminutive scale at the base with Buddha and Kalkin, at the midsection with the man-boar Varaha and man-lion Narasimha followed further out by Vamana and Balarama, and at the top with Matsya and Kurma.²¹ The composition culminates in the heavenly realm at the top of the statue, which, following the pattern of a door lintel, presents a triune godhead with Brahma and Shiva on either side of Vishnu each within a miniature shrine. This elaborate frame does not contain the principal deity, for Vishnu's broad shoulders and four arms extend forth to interrupt its verticality, emphasising his uncontainable and expansive nature. Similarly, the god's steepled crown, which rises up in vertical extension of his columnar body to be honoured by garland-bearers, alters the horizontality of the frame to highlight Vishnu's paramount position in the hierarchy

21. To determine the identity of some of these characters is sometimes a matter of comparison and deduction, for their attributes are hardly visible or not represented, as with the snake held by Garuda or Rama's arrow.

Figure 8. — Vishnu statues, 11th century, in storage at Sunari, showing details of the crown. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

of being. These compositional strategies thus lend the statues a distinct formal and conceptual monumentality.

The Vishnu statues are distinguished by their large size, complex composition, and monumentality that would only make sense if they were intended as the main focus of devotion in the sanctum of a temple.²² They vary in height from 1.30 to 1.50 metres, which makes them larger than the vast majority of wall images on post-10th century temples. For example, the figures animating the outer walls of the Udayeshwar temple at Udaypur measure 80–90 cm high. The average of the Sunari images places them above some of those enshrined in the largest temples in central India, since the Vishnu enshrined in the Lakshman temple at Khajuraho is about 1.21 metres.²³ Moreover, the composition of Sunari's images is much more complex than that of architectural sculptures designed to be placed in the central niches of a temple's outer wall. The mural sculptures at the Udayeshwar temple were either carved directly onto architectural blocks or on separate squared off slabs that were then set into niches, invariably framed by circular colonnettes. In contrast, the Sunari statues have a tapering crest, stepped base, and square pilasters framing the main deity. Further, as demonstrated above, the statues are distinguished by their monumentality, in both formal and conceptual terms, so that the size, number and arrangement of figures in the composition follows principles of upward hierarchy and outward emanation. The principal figure of the statues, unlike those of mural sculpture, exceeds his frame and is magnified in stature by a large set of subsidiary figures positioned around him in a tight composition at various scales of importance. These design features indicate that each of the Vishnu statues was meant to be installed individually in a temple sanctum.

22. Following the method developed by MASON 1993, pp. 128–129.

23. DESAI 1996, pp. 101, 214 dates this statue to the late 11th century, ca. 1075–1100 CE.

Figure 9. — Udayeshwar temple at Udaypur, 1080 CE (vikrama 1137), view of the tower from the west. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

If they are designed as the focal images of temples, the Vishnu statues are also conceived as temples in and of themselves. The metonymic relationship between temple and statuary is emphasised by the towering form of the supreme god that projects forth from a threshold, arrayed with his cosmic entourage from heaven to earth. A particularly revealing detail is the peculiar shape of Vishnu's tall crown that references at miniature scale the very form of a temple spire (*shikhara*) (figs. 8–9).²⁴ With its round or polygonal section, segmented elevation and serrated disc (*amalaka*),

24. This architectural conception of the headdress, though elaborated in a distinctive way at Sunari, can be seen across northern India more broadly. For example, the Lakshminarayana image from Khajuraho at the National Museum, New Delhi, no. 82.225; a Vishnu from eastern Madhya Pradesh in the Museum of Fine Arts, Boston, no. 25.438; and the Surya from Chapra belonging to the Varendra Research Museum, Rajshahi, no. VRM 242.

this micro-architectural shorthand highlights a series of correspondences between statue and sanctuary, interior and exterior, and part and whole. Intriguingly, the crowns on some Vishnu statues specifically evoke the distinctive spire of a temple built in the *bhūmija* style of architecture, as they have a central segment surrounded by vertical rows of small modules and are tightened towards the top where a large serrated disc protrudes.²⁵ Such steepled crowns are not encountered on Vishnu statues in central India before the 11th century, and their novelty attests to the iconic status attained by different types of temple spires with the rapid growth in architectural patronage at this time, particularly of *bhūmija* temples built under the Paramara dynasty in Malwa.²⁶

In the absence of any donative inscriptions on, or associated with, the Vishnu statues, an important clue for dating them is their stylistic homogeneity, seen in the structural frame of the statuary, the anatomical treatment and the ornamentation. The allusive modelling of Vishnu's body does not suggest heavy musculature but provides smooth areas that generate strong contrasts with the jewellery carved in relief. Body weight is concentrated in the upper torso, with broad and slightly drooping shoulders, and wide hips with a pronounced waist. The overall morphology tends towards an elongation of the human figure from the legs to the crown, corresponding to stylistic trends in central India during the 11th century, as attested by the Ambika from Dhar, now in the British Museum,²⁷ the door-guardians at Bhojpur,²⁸ the Jain goddesses at temple 19 in Deogarh,²⁹ and the mural sculpture at Kandariya Mahadev temple in Khajuraho.³⁰

The Vishnu statues of Sunari are also unified by the abundance and complexity of their ornamentation. Among the new decorative motifs that make their appearance in several Vishnu statues is the “flaming arch” crowning the miniature niches of Brahma and Shiva, an ornament used in western Indian temples that gained prominence in eastern Malwa and Bundelkhand, attested at Kadwaha in the late 10th century, Sihoniya *ca.* 1030, Ashapuri in the late 10th–early 11th century, and at Udaypur in 1080 CE.³¹ The sculptors' interest in the accumulation of decorative details finds close parallels in the Vishnu statue installed in the Lakshman temple of Khajuraho, although at Sunari the ornaments are more crisply carved, less undulating and heavier in form.³² Likewise, the stylisation of ornaments can be situated in broader 11th-century trends but their lively exuberance at Sunari is particularly

Figure 10a. — Vishnu statue, late 10th–early 11th century, Ashapuri. Sandstone, H. 109 cm. Birla Museum, Bhopal, no. 151. Photo: Johan Levillain.

striking, whether in Vishnu's steepled crown or in his handheld lotus, which is here transformed into the tiered lotiform pendant typically found ornamenting the centre of a temple ceiling.³³

The remarkable uniformity of Sunari's Vishnu statues would allow us to place them within a relatively short production phase in the 11th century, to which their frame, form and ornamentation correspond. The slight variations from one sculpture to the other, which are restricted mainly to the roundness of a cheek or the undulation of an eyebrow, appear to reflect subtle differences in craftsmanship around the same time. On the contrary, we find greater variation in groups of Vishnu statues created over several generations. Those at the royal centre of Khajuraho, carved between the mid-10th century and the late 11th century, display a high degree of variation in the number and placement of subsidiary figures as well as overall proportions. This variability is most apparent in the positioning of Vishnu's avatars, such that the most important avatars, Varaha and Narasimha, sometimes replace Brahma and Vishnu in the niches at the top of the statue.³⁴ An even greater diversity is seen in the 9th–11th-century statuary at Ashapuri, nearly 100 kilometres south of Sunari, where Vishnu's avatars are either grouped together at the top of the statue or arranged in a format comparable to Sunari and Khajuraho (fig. 10a). Moreover, the Sunari corpus exhibits no

25. DEVA 1975, HARDY 2014, and HARDY 2015, pp. 31–73.

26. On the iconic use of temple spires in 11th–13th-century Deccan, see DHAKY 1977.

27. British Museum, London, no. 1909,1224.1. See LEVILLAIN 2021.

28. HARDY 2015, p. 53.

29. BRUHN 1969, figs. 244, 248, 250, 256.

30. DESAI 1996, pp. 149–174.

31. SEARS 2015, pp. 59–62.

32. The jewellery and clothes worn by the Vishnus of Sunari find a compelling match in the Vishnu-Vaikuntha housed in the sanctum of the Lakshman temple of Khajuraho. If the temple itself is usually dated to 954 CE, the image of Vaikuntha seems to date from the late 11th century. See DESAI 1996, pp. 211–217.

33. See NANAVATI & DHAKY 1963, p. 37, plate 47 for a comparable temple ceiling with a central pendant projected out (*utksipta*).

34. In addition to the images still in their sanctum, see the images in the site museum illustrated by SURESH 1999, plates 3, 7, 8, 10, 11, 45.

Figure 10b. — Vishnu statue, dated 1185 CE (*vikrama* 1242), found at Lakheraghat, Vidisha. Gujari Mahal Museum, Gwalior, no. 144. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

addition or reduction of iconographic content, nor any alteration of formal vocabulary as to have any significant chronological consequence. The rich, elaborate execution also stands apart from the progressive tendency to simplify volumes and ornamentation seen in 12th-century sculptures, such as the rare dated statue of Vishnu from 1185 CE (*vikrama* 1242) found at Vidisha (fig. 10b).³⁵ We are therefore tempted to date the Sunari corpus more precisely to the second half of the 11th century, which is also consistent with the inscribed statue of Hanuman, dated 1063–1064 CE (see below).

Moreover, a detour to the extensively studied sculpture of Khajuraho confirms that the statues of Sunari are indeed part of a more global aesthetic prevalent in central India at the end of the 11th century that precedes subsequent developments. Here, sculptures of the early 11th century already display highly idealised anatomies, but they retain a preference for stocky and

rounded volumes,³⁶ which is distinguishable from the increasingly abstract and geometric volumes that preoccupied the next generation of sculptors, both at Khajuraho and at Sunari. Among the statues still *in situ* at Khajuraho's temples and those stored at the local archaeological museum that may be dated between the late 11th and 12th centuries, many display characteristics common to the statues of Sunari.³⁷ They have a greater sense of monumentality and extension of openwork areas; increasingly slender bodies with long legs and high headdresses, including hair buns that have little in common with their rounder counterparts of earlier times; an accumulation of detail in adornment and costume, with an increase in secondary fabric belts and chains forming multiple sets of loops on the thighs; and an increase in the complexity of decorative elements borrowed from architecture, not only in the general arrangement of pilasters and arches behind the main figure, but also in the *sikhara*-like form of Vishnu's crown.

The presence of more than a dozen statues of Vishnu at a single site, identical in their material, format and iconography and comparable in their size, composition and style, points to the existence of a sculptors' workshop at Sunari. The overall homogeneity of the corpus remains unbroken even when certain iconographic components of the layout are altered to give each statue a discreet individuality. The most prominent reconfigurations of detail include the repositioning of Garuda at reduced scale behind the Buddha, instead of in his usual place among the six mid-sized figures attending Vishnu; the shifting of the equestrian avatar Kalkin from the base to the top of the vertical uprights; the appearance of Varaha and Narasimha as the only two avatars at the midsection of the uprights in four statues while Vamana and Balarama are placed elsewhere; and the alternation of the personified conch and disc to the right or left of Vishnu. The variations can be more subtle as when subsidiary figures in their fixed positions are represented differently. Thus, the Buddha, usually shown seated in meditation, appears standing in one instance; Varaha who is occasionally represented without the goddess Bhu on his elbow; Narasimha who can be represented fighting against the demon he has not yet overthrown or gutting the demon he has already mastered; only once is the Earth goddess on the base shown without her snake-hood; and most surprisingly, Vishnu twice replaces Shiva at the top of the statue.³⁸ Thus, if everything had been consciously thought out but voluntarily applied, the Sunari corpus would be a remarkable outcome of modular production, where

35. Gujari Mahal Museum, Gwalior, no. 144. For the inscription, see ARIE 1964–1965, p. 135, appendix C, no. 2199.

36. See LORENZETTI 2000, pp. 17–19 for images from the Varaha temple (first quarter of the 11th century), and the Nara-Varaha now at the local archaeological museum.

37. See LORENZETTI 2000, pp. 12–14, 42–43 for the sanctum image of the Chaturbhuj temple (late 11th century) and two particularly revealing examples, Vishnu-Vaikuntha and Ambika.

38. Moreover, it seems that when Vishnu takes the place of Shiva, Brahma on the other side is represented single-headed.

Figure 11. — Vishnu statue, 11th century, Sunari. Sandstone, H. 101.6 cm. Vidisha District Museum, no. 1916. Photo: Johan Levillain.

Figure 12a (left). — Statue of Brahma, 11th century, Sunari. Sandstone. In storage at Sunari. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

Figure 12b (right). — Statue of Parvati, 11th century, Sunari. Sandstone. Vidisha District Museum, no. 1914. Photo: Johan Levillain.

each element could be organised by the sculptor in response to given specifications from a basic scheme that constitutes the signature of the workshop. From this perspective, certain variations that seem idiosyncratic may actually be quite purposeful, as we find in the singular instance where the privileged place of auspiciousness and allegiance at the right side of Vishnu's feet is occupied not by a male devotee but by a female figure kneeling with palms joined in homage, a choice that suggests the statue was commissioned by a woman (fig. 11).³⁹

The modularity of sculptural production can be discerned in other iconographic types too. A statue of Brahma and another of Parvati both have the same structural frame as that used for Vishnu, especially the stepped base and uprights with attendant figures overlapping each other (fig. 12). Similarly, openwork carving is used to highlight the principal figures as well as the subsidiary figures on the outermost upright. The deities have the same standing posture as Vishnu, with their feet firmly fixed together, and it is only by the alteration of appropriate iconographic details that they attain distinct identities: Brahma armed with scripture, ladle, water-pot, and lotus stands upon his goose vehicle flanked by bearded male attendants, while

39. For the longstanding auspicious symbolism attached to a god's right side, see BAKKER 2019.

Figure 13a. — Multi-armed statue of Ganesha, 11th century, Sunari. Sandstone. In storage at Sunari. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

Parvati stands upon her lizard cognisance with female attendants on either side and her fires of austerity on the uprights. That these statues were produced around the same time shows workshop practice was not bound to sectarian affiliation since the distinctive format was not exclusive to Vishnu statuary but was replicable as required, a key feature of modular production that has clearly led to the misidentification of Parvati as Vishnu at the Vidisha Museum.

With increasingly complex iconography, indices of modular thinking become more recognisable. A multi-armed statue of Ganesha and another of Vishnu on his aquiline mount both present a monumental seated figure, whose numerous handheld attributes together assume the form of a circular aureole around the deity (figs. 13a, 13b). The weapons they hold all have long shafts that look very similar, but are distinguished only at their extremities as arrows, axe, rod, noose, and so on. The visual assimilation of all these iconographic details indicates that what

Figure 13b. — Multi-armed statue of Vishnu-on-Garuda, 11th century, Sunari. Sandstone. Vidisha District Museum, no. 1910. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

Figure 13c. — Multi-armed statue of Vishnu-on-Garuda, 11th century, Udaypur. Sandstone. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

was at stake was not so much their individuality as their serial accumulation, designed to vividly portray the military might of these deities. A number of unfinished statues from Udaypur reveal the working methods of dealing with iconographic complexity (fig. 13c). A multi-armed image of Vishnu seated on Garuda shows how a block of stone squared to the required dimensions was first fully outlined with the composition, then carved down along the outlines to round off the volumes, before details of ornaments and accessories would have been added.⁴⁰

The subject of workshop production is sparsely documented in the subcontinent, and especially in central India.⁴¹ The ethnographic research of John F. Mosteller on surviving traditions

of carving figural stone statues in south India provides some insight into the methods and advantages of workshop production in mediaeval India.⁴² He highlights the fundamental importance of drawing in the creative process, which allows the sculptor to establish the rough outlines of a composition as well as the proportions of an image.⁴³ The use of drawing has practical advantages since it facilitates the replication of images and guarantees a certain accuracy in the iconography, but it also ensures the efficacy of a cult image giving form to the god. On an equally practical level, modular production also gives flexibility

40. Following DEHEJIA & ROCKWELL 2016, pp. 183–184 this would conform to the “cookie-cutter” rather than “front plane” technique.

41. The organisation of mediaeval workshops has been explored in the context of temple construction by MISRA 2009, and in the context of tombstones carved for Muslim patrons in Gujarat by LAMBOURN 2004.

42. MOSTELLER 1988a.

43. Drawing is not limited to this preliminary stage however, since the progressive carving of the stone necessitates the contours of the figure to be traced again as they are drawn out from the material. From then on, the act of drawing accompanies the entire creative process. Moreover, drawing is at the heart of a workshop’s identity, since a master first transmits a line to his students, who memorise it and learn to reproduce it, even before being familiar with the chisel or three-dimensional morphologies. See MOSTELLER 1987, p. 56; and MOSTELLER 1988a, pp. 25–26.

Figure 14a. — Architectural sculpture of Surya, Udayeshwar temple, Udaypur, 1080 CE. Photo: Johan Levillain.

Figure 14b. — Architectural sculpture of Skanda, Udayeshwar temple, Udaypur, 1080 CE. Photo: Johan Levillain.

to the overall scheme and makes the iconographic motifs interchangeable, likely to appeal to a wide range of patrons. In that way, the structure of Sunari's images would be modular in both iconography and technique, like the Chinese paintings of the underworld studied by Lothar Ledderose, which offered an interesting point of comparison for our own study.⁴⁴ Unlike painters, however, it is hard to imagine that sculptors used actual stencils, although their interest in replication is obvious. They preferred modular grids to give the images their proportions, which is a surviving practice that Mosteller acknowledges in Tamil Nadu,⁴⁵ and which was already in former times discussed in the normative texts dealing with iconometry.⁴⁶ Unfortunately, mediaeval times left little concrete evidence of drawing in sculpture. Most often it concerns lines incised in stone for the carving of architectural elements.⁴⁷

Whether the temple statues found at Sunari were made for local patrons or for export to other places such as Udaypur is an imponderable at this stage. At Sunari, there are hardly any surface remains of stone temples that might have enshrined so many Vishnu statues. While it is entirely possible that they were installed in structures of less durable materials than stone,⁴⁸ the installation of more than a dozen statues of the same

iconographic type in the same place is unprecedented even at major centres of sculptural production. At Ashapuri, where ruins of more than twenty temples are documented at the heart of the complex, there are only about nine fragmentary statues dedicated to Vaishnava worship. Similarly, at Khajuraho, where twenty-two monumental temples are still extant, there are few Vishnu statues that compare in size and stylistic consistency to those of Sunari.⁴⁹ While it is doubtful that Sunari was meant to provide an architectural setting for all the statues, the export of finished sculptures is even more unusual, since it is generally assumed that stone carving in the premodern period was a local craft, built around local sources of stone, with imports being restricted to specific geographical zones.⁵⁰ In the Malwa region, rivers are rarely used for transportation of goods, because they remain unnavigable for most of their extent due to the high seasonal fluctuation in waterflow; they are, however, used to ferry goods and people across, as links to overland routes traversed by bullock carts.⁵¹ Thus, it is possible that the statues recovered

44. LEDDEROSE 2000.

45. MOSTELLER 1987.

46. MOSTELLER 1988b.

47. See the study of the Bhojpur drawings in HARDY 2015, pp. 38–69.

48. The use of brick is documented in the *bhūmija* towers of the royal temples at Panaheda dated 1059 CE and Arthuna 1080 CE in TRIVEDI P.K. 1995, pp. 29, 35. At

Khajuraho, brick mounds near the royal Shiva temple of Vaidyanatha have been interpreted as monasteries for brahmins, in DEVA 1990. The possibility that small flat-roofed shrines called *mandapika* were also crowned by brick towers was noted by HARDY 2015, p. 168.

49. DEVA 1990, DESAI 1996.

50. ROCKWELL 1993, pp. 2–3; and DEHEJIA & ROCKWELL 2016, pp. 125–126. The two documented exceptions are in Bengal and Gujarat. ASHER 1998 shows that geological imperatives in the Pala-Sena domains of eastern India drove the transregional export of quarried stone, although the production of finished sculptures was localised. LAMBOURN 2004 discusses Gujarati export of marble carvings for Muslim patrons around the Indian Ocean rim.

51. JHA 2008, p. 295.

Figure 15a. — Temple statuary of the 11th century preserved in open-air shrine at the village of Sunari. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

from the riverbed accidentally sank at a ferrying point near the centre of production, unless they were purposefully deposited for reasons that elude us today. In the absence of comparative evidence from central India, the transport of heavy stone statuary remains a hypothesis that would require further investigation.⁵²

If the production of freestanding statuary was localised at specific places under sedentary workshops, architectural sculpture along with other structural components had to be carved on site and often required the movement of craftsmen.⁵³ At Udaypur, the building of the Udayeshwar temple involved the collaboration of multiple workshops, which are documented by hundreds of mason marks as well as by the differences in stylistic treatment.⁵⁴ Some of the architectural sculpture at this site is reminiscent of Sunari's idiom, as seen in a high-relief image of the sun god Surya, which displays the same posture, anatomy and ornamentation as that of Vishnu—down to details of the full square face and the steepled crown, even if the decorative richness is somewhat reduced due to its secondary status in the overall program (fig. 14a). Other sculptures, however, display a different stylistic idiom indebted to the Paramara heartlands of Dhar and Ujjain in western Malwa. Thus, a stele of Skanda affixed in a

cardinal niche of the sanctuary presents the war-god with much more slender and elongated limbs than the Vishnus of Sunari, with a pronounced bend at the waist that recalls the posture of the renowned Ambika statue from Dhar, and a crown of tapering tiers typically seen in royal Paramara production (fig. 14b).⁵⁵ It is, therefore, likely that at least two sculptural workshops were engaged at the royal temple of Udaypur, one employing a local tradition and another the privileged dynastic one. The involvement of multiple workshops in the building of major temples has also been noted at other sites in Malwa, where local and distant idioms were brought together under dynastic patronage.⁵⁶

Art historical assessment of style and idiom is almost exclusively based on sculptures in museums or at major temple sites, while those gathered for worship on countless village *cabūtrās* are ignored because they are either too fragmentary or covered by accretions of ritual adornment. But when seen in the context of Sunari's statuary, the sculptural assemblages at village sites present a rare glimpse into the richness of artistic production throughout the countryside, as against its concentration at a few urban centres. At Sunari itself, the weathered fragments on the *cabūtrā* near the reservoir bear close correspondence in scale, format and style to the statues recovered from the riverbed (fig. 15a). But the Sunari workshop was probably not as exceptional, for fragmentary statues found at Purwai, Jhilipur, Khurseni and Negma in the vicinity of Udaypur (see

52. See DESAI 1996, pp. 211–217 for the rare case of an “imported” Vishnu statue of Himalayan provenance, said to have been seized by the Chandella king and installed in the Lakshman temple at Khajuraho in 954 CE.

53. ASHER 1998, pp. 326–327 offers a broader discussion on the relationship between sedentary and itinerant artists.

54. ARIE 1981–1982, pp. 50–86, nos. 111–543, and ARIE 1982–1983, pp. 30–110, nos. 21–803.

55. See LEVILLAIN 2021.

56. HARDY 2015.

Figure 15b. — Temple statuary of the 11th century preserved in open-air shrine at the village of Purwai. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

map 3) display the same characteristics, from the structural frame and openwork carving to the overlapping of subsidiary figures, but are distinguished by their iconographic choices and stylistic treatment. A Vishnu statue preserved at Purwai features a distinct iconographic formula with Lakshmi placed to the right of the god and Garuda to his left, Kalkin and Buddha on the uprights and Varaha and Narasimha at the top of the image (fig. 15b). Among elements of local idioms that stand out from a more global trend is the treatment of anatomical form, as seen in a statue of Shiva-Parvati at Negma that displays slimmer, tubular torsos and narrower waists (fig. 15c). These sculptural remains merit a fuller analysis elsewhere, but are suggestive enough of the vitality of local idioms during the 11th century,

Figure 15c. — Temple statuary of the 11th century preserved in open-air shrine at the village of Negma. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

which retained their distinctiveness while reinforcing broader stylistic coherence.

As the foregoing analysis shows, the large-scale production of freestanding temple statuary at Sunari was facilitated by modular methods, which enabled a greater complexity of frame, form and ornamentation to develop a concrete sense of monumentality, while allowing flexibility in organising iconographic details for Vaishnava and Shaiva images alike. Far from being dry and uninspired, however, the products of this local workshop have an unusual liveliness and display of technical virtuosity that distinguishes them in larger networks of production, encompassing imperial projects at Udaypur as well as smaller (but no less monumental) works in its hinterland.

Seriality and creativity in monolithic Varaha sculptures

A staggering sense of how Sunari's master sculptors manipulated ideas of monumentality and seriality to dramatic effect appears in two monolithic sculptures of Varaha, which show the massive body of the Boar incarnation of Vishnu entirely carved with miniature images of divinities from the Hindu pantheon (figs. 5–6). Both sculptures measure about 1.35 metres in height, but unlike the Vishnu statues, they are carved in-the-round and thus exude a more imposing sense of magnitude. Their large size distinguishes them from other freestanding sculptures of Varaha found at major centres in the Paramara kingdom, only a few of which come close in their dimensions, most being less than a metre high.⁵⁷

The colossal scale may be peculiar to eastern Malwa where we find a series of huge Varaha sculptures. These include one of the oldest zoomorphic representations at Eran, which was installed around 500 CE after the Huna conquest of the Gupta Empire and remains the largest to date at 3.65 metres high.⁵⁸ In subsequent centuries, the patronage of Varaha sculptures was perpetuated throughout the Betwa valley, both in the Paramara kingdom at sites such as Gyaraspur and Vidisha, and in the Chandella domains at Dudhai and Chandpur.⁵⁹ Its particular importance in the environs of Sunari is highlighted by the presence of two temples dedicated to Varaha: one at Badoh-Pathari, dating to the 10th century, held a statue measuring 1.5 metres high,⁶⁰ while the other at Muradpur, dating to the 11th century, shelters an even larger statue standing 2.5 metres high.⁶¹

Beyond size, the monumentality of these sculptures derives from a compelling mythological narrative in the Puranas about Vishnu's incarnation as a triumphant Boar who rescues the Earth from the deluge at the time of destruction.⁶² As visualised in zoomorphic form, the snouted saviour appears in a heroic stance, having emerged from the watery depths, effortlessly supporting the Earth goddess on his tusked snout, as her inhabitants take refuge in his ample body. The iconographic details follow an established canon, with some regional variations, as scholars have discussed in detail.⁶³ What is remarkable in these representations is the serialised depiction of gods and sages

carved in miniature on the Boar's body and densely packed in concentric circuits within the larger whole. This arrangement has striking parallels with the visual density of mediaeval temples, whose walls are similarly crowded with sculptures of mortals and immortals, in emulation of the concentric, crowded topography of the Puranic heavens.⁶⁴ If such temples took on a sculptural quality, so did sculptures of Varaha assume an architectural appeal, with the disposition of figural imagery in concentric bands designed to elicit circumambulatory engagement. At Sunari this idea is further emphasised by images of the eight directional guardians (*dikpālas*), which are carved in pairs on the four legs of the Boar, as they would be on the corners of a temple.⁶⁵ Incidentally, their arrangement gives us a clue to the original orientation of the Varaha sculptures: both have the right foreleg carved with the guardians of the east (Indra) and southeast (Agni), indicating that the images were designed to face east.⁶⁶

The portrayal of Varaha as rescuer of the Earth also retains an older, cosmogonic understanding of his role in stabilising the universe. The elaborate vision, read from the base upwards, has the tortoise as the firm foundation of the three realms—an aqueous underworld at the boar's feet, inhabited by the serpentine Shesha with his aquiline adversary Garuda; a terrestrial world on the boar's body, populated by serried sequences of deities seeking refuge; and a heavenly world on the boar's head and back—the whole crowned by a miniature shrine forming the top of the cosmic pillar.⁶⁷ A large part of the symbolism is drawn from Vedic cosmology, where Varaha's body parts are systematically identified with elements of the sacrifice (*yajña*), so that the head is associated with Brahman, the shoulders with the altar, and the stump or shrine over the shoulders with the sacrificial post (*yūpa*).⁶⁸ The symbolism of the pillar and altar underlying the "sacrificial boar" (*yajñavarāha*) also informs the plan and elevation of north Indian temples,⁶⁹ thus providing a clear conceptual basis to make sense of Varaha's cosmic symbolism in specifically microarchitectural terms. Moreover, in the landmark Eran inscription, the image of the Boar (*varāhamūrti*) is described not only as a "pillar for the three worlds of the universe" (*trailokya-mahāgrha-stambhaḥ*) but also as a "stone temple of Narayana" (*nārāyaṇasya śilāprāsādaḥ*), despite itself being installed in a structural shrine.⁷⁰

57. See RANGARAJAN 1997, pp. 108, 113–121, 125, and the more extensive survey by RENNER 2012, pp. 265–294.

58. See BECKER 2010 and, more recently, CECIL & BISSCHOP 2021.

59. The two sculptures from Gyaraspur remain unpublished. For those from Vidisha, see RENNER 2012, pp. 274–277; those from Dudhai and Chandpur, see RANGARAJAN 1997, pp. 92–105 and RENNER 2012, pp. 253–264.

60. Now at the Gujari Mahal Museum, Gwalior, no. 108; see CASILE 2009, III, pp. 66–67 for its architectural context.

61. RAG 2007, pp. 109–110; ANSARI 2012. An early photograph from 1905 may be found at the Kern Institute, Leiden, no. P-043052.

62. PRASAD 1989.

63. RANGARAJAN 1997, pp. 34–46 and RENNER 2012, pp. 101–122.

64. GRANOFF 1997.

65. This convention is also found in Chandella sculpture at Khajuraho, Dudhai and Chandpur; see RANGARAJAN 1997, pp. 69–82, 95–104, 104–105.

66. The positions of the *dikpālas* are reversed in the colossal Varaha at Khajuraho, which is still *in situ* within an open pillared pavilion (*maṇḍapa*) and faces west towards the lakeside royal temple to Vishnu founded in 954 CE. See DESAI 1996, pp. 64–69.

67. BECKER 2010, pp. 130–132 reviews the different interpretations of the box-like structure on the back.

68. AGRAWALA 1963, pp. 15–18 discusses the textual comparison in greater detail.

69. MEISTER 1986, pp. 36–39.

70. FLEET 1888, p. 160, verse 1, recently discussed in Cecil & BISSCHOP 2021, pp. 47–48.

At Sunari, this complex system of symbols and iconographic elements was mobilised in highly original and innovative ways to advance a distinct attitude of worldliness. Both sculptures show the Boar's head raised in heroic triumph but turned slightly towards the right, in a jovial gesture towards the Earth goddess, who—oblivious to the peril of the waters from which she has just been saved—caresses Varaha's right tusk as his mouth opens in a benevolent smile. In orchestrating this playful dalliance and sensuous relationship, the sculptor portrays the Earth not as a damsel in distress hanging helplessly off Varaha's tusk, but as a dignified companion of her divine saviour with whom she stands shoulder-to-shoulder, at a larger scale and in the guise of a queen.⁷¹ The liveliness and dynamism orchestrated here is in sharp contrast to the more rigid, emotionally distant and restrained monumentality of Varaha sculptures dependent on an older tradition, such as those from Badoh-Pathari, Muradpur and even Khajuraho, where the emphasis is on the herculean efforts of the saviour, rather than his relationship to the earth. The Sunari sculptures thus signal a palpable shift in artistic intention aimed at creating a new kind of worldly interest in the otherwise abstract symbolism of the cosmic boar.

In addition to the general attitude common to the two Sunari sculptures, the similar arrangement of distinctive elements on and around Varaha's body points to a common model. The head is crowned by a row of deities and the neck carries a necklace of thick pearls. On his left side, intertwined with a thick lotus stem is a three-hooded serpent, not to be confused with those winding up Varaha's tail or the serpent-king Shesha carved on the base. The organisation of the decor on the back follows a similar scheme, with Vishnu and Lakshmi framed in concentric circles just behind the head, followed by an image of Surya.⁷² On each leg is a pair of *dikpālas* placed in identical positions on both sculptures, and a snake-hood adorning the forepart of the hooves. Secondary characters are also arranged identically. The earth goddess stands playfully to the right of the god. A tortoise takes its place under Varaha and Shesha,⁷³ whose tail passes between the Boar's legs, has three hoods and faces the devotee with folded hands. Despite his badly mutilated appearance, it is possible to discern the figure of Garuda facing Varaha slightly to his left.⁷⁴ Such visual proximity leaves little doubt that these two sculptures are the products of the same workshop.

71. RENNER 2012, pp. 278–279 comes to similar conclusions but takes this further, as indicating the value and perception of women at this time.

72. In the Vidisha museum statue, RENNER 2012, p. 280, identifies the central figures of the mandala as Shiva-Parvati, followed by Vishnu-on-Garuda to one side. But the Varaha at Sunari, to which she did not have access, confirms our identification.

73. On Varaha no. 1, the tortoise merges with the rectangular base, on the sides of which its legs are sculpted in very low relief.

74. The iconography of the cosmic boar at Sunari can be situated within a broader iconographic tradition prevalent in the Betwa valley, straddling the Chandella and Paramara kingdoms, a subject we set aside for a separate occasion.

Figure 16. — Schematic diagram illustrating details of Varaha no. 1 (left) and no. 2 (right). Drawing: Johan Levillain.

Variations of iconography and style suggest that the two sculptures were not carved at the exact same time, although the gap between them is not very large (fig. 16). Compared to the sculpture now in the Vidisha museum (no. 1), the Varaha still in Sunari (no. 2) presents an expanded repertoire of figures on the body and the base. Prominent additions to its iconography include an additional band of seated figures around the neck; the figure of Brahma seated atop a lotus on the thick stalk intertwined with a serpent; on the same side, three ovoid medallions representing the oceans in the fifth register from the top; and on the forepart of each hoof, a *samudrarāja* or “ocean-king” riding a water monster. The arrangement of some figures is reconfigured, as in the case of Vishnu's avatars, who usually appear among the rows of deities on the body but are distinguished here by their positioning on the base. There is a greater density of imagery on the body, resulting in narrower registers and a more formulaic treatment of individual figures, so that they are difficult to distinguish except as part of a sequence: the 12 solar deities (*ādityas*), the 9 astral deities (*navagrahas*), and so on.

The idea of density is also developed in decorative terms, as seen in the multiple necklaces and elaborate head ornament of the Boar. Thus, the more elaborate iconographic and ornamental features of Varaha no. 2 lead us to believe that it was produced some time after its counterpart.

From a stylistic perspective, Varaha no. 1 is closer to older sculptures in the region, such as those from Badoh-Pathari and Muradpur.⁷⁵ Varaha no. 2, on the other hand, gives off a sense of sensuous naturalism in its slender physique, slim legs, and an elongated snout that turns triumphantly to one side, corresponding to broader trends of increasingly attenuated and elongated anatomical forms.⁷⁶ However, the treatment of details is drier and more stylised: the Earth goddess has a stiffer attitude compared to the fluid posture seen in Varaha no. 1, and recalls the modelling of the dancing women on the walls of the temple at Udaypur.⁷⁷ She is more richly adorned and her headdress, a long coiled wick brought back to the top of the head, recalls decorative forms from the Paramara heartlands, as seen in the Ambika from Dhar.⁷⁸ A useful dated comparison from eastern Malwa is provided by the Varaha sculpture at Chandpur dated 1146 CE (*vikrama* 1203),⁷⁹ which bears significant parallels to the Varaha no. 2. Unlike the flat, blocky volumes of older images, both offer a more naturalistic vision of the animal, with drawn out and slender volumes, attentive to anatomical articulations of the legs and the curvature of the hindquarters.

Based as much on this formal evolution as on dated milestones, Varaha no. 1 therefore appears older and we propose to situate it around the middle of the 11th century, at a time when the more stylised volumes and bold attitudes did not completely set aside the rigid monumentality of the past. The Varaha no. 1 embodies, then, the culmination of a monumental iconographic tradition of regional significance that subsequently served as a model for the creation of Varaha no. 2, towards the late 11th century or early 12th century, but which is a receptacle of extra-regional contributions that have enriched the basic regional scheme.⁸⁰ Varaha no. 2 also displays this now typical monumentality marked by a prominent sensuality, stylised volumes and above all a kind of compositional and decorative treatment that emphasises the global rendering of the image rather than its individual components.

The occurrence of two colossal sculptures of Varaha at a single place is highly unusual. Scholars have noted the political

Figure 17. — Varaha sculpture *in situ* within its temple at Muradpur, 11th century. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

resonances of Varaha in other contexts,⁸¹ which would suggest that the production of these sculptures was linked to a resurgence of political interest in its imagery during the 11th century. The rhetoric of “the Boar rescuing the Earth from Deluge” can be read in direct relation to Udaypur, where the imprint of imperial authority was made dramatically visible in the construction works consecrated by Udayaditya in 1080 CE. The patron was celebrated in a number of dynastic inscriptions throughout Malwa as the one who liberated the Paramara kingdom after it was overtaken by a “sea of enemies.” One such poetic reference appears in a well-known inscription from Udaypur, which describes Udayaditya as “having restored the primaeval Boar without difficulty.”⁸² The editor of the inscription, H.V. Trivedi, perceptively saw this as “a hint to the restoration of a Boar-temple by Udayāditya,” and one scholar has recently proposed to identify it with the surviving temple at Muradpur (**fig. 17**).⁸³ However, the evidence of multiple monolithic Varaha sculptures in and around Udaypur points to a broader investment in the salvific imagery of the cosmic boar. The point is illustrated by a smaller fragmentary sculpture of Varaha found at Udaypur itself, and another from Vidisha, both of which display an iconographic scheme very close to that of the second sculpture

75. For a discussion of the statue from Badoh-Pathari, see RENNER 2012, pp. 269–274, and RANGARAJAN 2015; and for Muradpur, RENNER 2012, pp. 282–285.

76. MASON 1993, p. 125.

77. AIIIS negative no. 75.61.

78. LEVILLAIN 2021.

79. ANSARI 2012, p. 32, fig. 3. AIIIS negative nos. 479.33–479.37.

80. A discussion of the broader iconographic tradition prevalent in the Betwa valley, straddling the Chandella and Paramara kingdoms, has been set aside for another occasion.

81. ASHER 1983, WILLIS 2009, and BECKER 2010.

82. TRIVEDI H.V. 1978, pp. 80–81, verse 22.

83. ANSARI 2012, pp. 29–31.

Figure 18. — Varaha sculpture, ca. 11th century, Vidisha. Photos: Saarthak Singh.

from Sunari (**fig. 18**).⁸⁴ Thus, whether or not it was prompted by royal precedent, the image of Varaha appears to have gained greater currency at this time with a range of patrons, who facilitated its replication across the countryside, at different scales of monumentality and affective possibility.

The “worldly” vision of Varaha, as the staggering image of cosmic order but also a sophisticated lover in dalliance with the Earth goddess, would have surely marked a momentous intervention in the landscape. The iconography of the aquatic realm at Varaha’s feet, with snakes still coiled around his body, suggests that the Sunari sculptures were installed in some meaningful topographic relation to a reservoir or riverfront. This ecological dimension is well attested by the 5th-century rock-cut tableau at Udayagiri in which Varaha’s feet, emerging from the cosmic waters rendered by wavy lines, were actually washed by water from a large tank facing the image, thus reenacting the mythical rescue of the earth every rainy season.⁸⁵ The continuity of such a pattern in the 11th–12th centuries is documented by the temples at Muradpur and Chandpur, both situated on the edge of a tank,⁸⁶ and by an epigraphic record of a Varaha temple established “on the banks of the Betwa river” (*vetravatyās=taṭa-bhuvī*) by the Paramara king Trailokyavarman in 1158–1160 CE (*vikrama* 1216).⁸⁷ In these contexts, Varaha may have served as a powerful memorial to the restoration of dynastic rule over a given territory, both in images enshrined with royal endowment and in those set up by subordinates. But at a more mundane level, the scores of such sculptures—large and small, from the composed to the combative—also stood as heroic agents of growth in a primarily agrarian landscape, addressing their audience with the visual rhetoric of “restoring” the earth as it is periodically submerged in the monsoon rains.

84. The sculpture was found in the western outskirts of Udaypur and is now relocated to the Pisanrika temple.

85. WILLIS 2009, p. 42.

86. ANSARI 2012, p. 31; MUKHERJI 1899, p. 31, plate 28.

87. TRIVEDI H.V. 1978, pp. 141–144, lines 3–4.

Sculpture as social intervention: Hanuman in the hinterland

How such freestanding monumental sculptures operated in the local contexts where they were installed as objects of worship is often implicitly understood in terms of divine agency, whether invested through rituals of consecration (*pratiṣṭhā*) or invoked through devotional eulogies (*stotra*). But to account for the specific ways in which broad theological conceptions of a divinity were materialised in sculpture, we must attend to the formal characteristics that define its rhetorical and affective abilities to act upon its interlocutors. Even if there is insufficient evidence to reconstruct a detailed local context of interaction, an object-oriented framework might help make better sense of the sculptures’ dynamism.

Unlike the well-preserved sculptures from Sunari discussed so far, the damaged fragments weathering for centuries on the village *cabūtrā* include the torso and the base of a large statue of Hanuman (**fig. 19a**). The old *gadhi* in the village has a large head of Hanuman, which was recovered from the riverbed and thus preserves details of its exquisite carving, but appears to have belonged to this very statue judging by the matching breakage on the head and the torso. Based on measurements of the head (45 × 28 cm), the base (64 × 62 cm) and the torso (72 cm high), and accounting for the missing arms and legs, the Hanuman statue would have stood approximately 2 metres in height. This makes it the tallest statue from Sunari, overshadowing even the sculptures of Vishnu and Varaha. The pedestal includes a one-line inscription in indistinct letters, ending with numerals that give the year 1120, the *vikrama* era equivalent to 1063–1064 CE.⁸⁸

The fragmentary form of the statue today makes it difficult to fully appreciate its intended effects, but since it belongs to an iconographic convention widely prevalent in mediaeval times, it is possible to identify some basic parameters of its force field. Among the few, firmly dateable milestones is a Hanuman statue in Khajuraho, installed in 922 CE, which is still intact and in worship on the banks of a reservoir (**fig. 19b**).⁸⁹ The two-metre-tall sculpture shows the protagonist standing tall in triumph, anchored on his right leg, with his left bent to trample a diminutive pair of enemies. His hands display emphatic gestures of warning: the left hand held at chest-level with its index finger raised, and the right hand poised overhead as if to strike a blow. This direct message of deterrence is underscored by the protruding eyes and a pronounced jaw, which gives Hanuman his distinctive monkey-like defiance. The deity is thus represented *in media res*, pinning down his enemies yet ready to ward-off impending evil.

88. The inscription is unpublished and the reading was made on site; see SINGH S. 2020 for photographs.

89. CUNNINGHAM 1871, II, p. 437; CUNNINGHAM 1880, p. 13, plate ix; and DESAI 1996, p. 21.

^ Figure 20. — Detail of fig. 19a, the head of the Hanuman statue at Sunari. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

< Figure 19a (left). — Hanuman statue in three fragments, dated 1063–1064 CE, Sunari. Sandstone, about 200 cm. In storage at Sunari. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

Figure 19b (right). — Hanuman statue, dated 922 CE, in worship at Khajuraho. Photo: John C. Huntington, Courtesy of the John C. and Susan L. Huntington Photographic Archive of Buddhist and Asian Art, no. 14448.

This dramatic conceptualisation of Hanuman as a monkey hero engaged in heroic exploits draws upon his decisive role in the epic quest of Rama, the god-king and avatar of Vishnu, as narrated in the *Ramayana*. He is praised in the epic above all for his superhuman strength, here emphasised by the sheer physicality and dramatic body language.⁹⁰ Unlike other gods saddled with numerous weapons, he appears unarmed except for a punch dagger knotted onto his waistband, which appears as a common accessory of various divinities by this time. In addition, Hanuman's tail appears coiled around the back like a hidden projectile, but it also serves as an object of worship cradled by a miniaturised devotee below his arm.⁹¹ Several episodes, omitted from the critical edition but popular in regional retellings of the *Ramayana*, describe Hanuman's contests with a number of terrifying female demons on his mission to the great demon city of Lanka, including its guardian Lankini, who may be identified with the skeletal female figure trapped underfoot.⁹² The accompanying sword-wielding male warrior is probably Ahiravana, the shadowy subterranean sorcerer defeated by Hanuman in vernacular versions of the epic.⁹³

90. GOLDMAN & GOLDMAN 1996, pp. 39–57.

91. The function of Hanuman's tail as an invincible weapon and as an object of devotion has been discussed by LUTGENDORF 2007, pp. 141–142, 200–202 and 293.

92. PANDEY 1993–1994.

93. LUTGENDORF 2007, pp. 149–156, 211–216.

Surviving fragments of the Sunari sculpture reveal the exceptional treatment of this subject when compared to the Khajuraho statue. The head, in particular, shows well developed volumes that lend a much more individualised expression of belligerence, from the menacing jaw parted to bare two rows of teeth to the large eyeballs bulging out of their sockets (fig. 20). The details are delicately carved to pick out individual curls of hair and to delineate flame-like ornaments on a tiered, tapering headdress, which is identical to the one crowning the Ganesh statue (see fig. 13a). The expressiveness and decorative enrichment of the head is comparable to two Hanuman statues from the fortress of Hinglajgarh in northwest Malwa, both attributed to a workshop that reached its apogee under Paramara rule in the 11th century and celebrated for its sensitivity of expression and refinement of detail.⁹⁴

Sunari's sculptors applied the same consummate skill to this statue of Hanuman as they did to those of Vishnu. The modelling of the torso is marked by a sharp bend above the curve of the hip, here giving the figure a sense of dynamic action as if his body had turned to face front. The details are worn out, but the elaborate system of jewellery follows that of Vishnu, with a rhomboidal jewel on the chest and multiple strands of necklace, belt and thigh ornaments, which are in stylistic agreement with

94. ATHERTON 1996, p. 563; JOSHI 1981, p. 115; and PARIMOO 2000.

Figure 21a. — Hanuman statue in three fragments at an open-air shrine (*cabūtrā*) at Siyari. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

Figure 21b. — Detail of the coiled tail at the back of the torso. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

the date of the inscription. What distinguishes this work from others at Sunari is the gripping portrayal of combat, conveyed by a raised finger of warning at the chest, a large hilted dagger tied to the waist with an elaborate double-looped knot, and a skeletal adversary clutching a similar dagger below. As such, the sculpture presents a more spirited and engaging performance than the somewhat static, reserved figure at Khajuraho.

The unusual prominence of Hanuman is not peculiar to Sunari but also characterises neighbouring villages, which are rarely without a large freestanding statue of this deity, and often have multiple such statues.⁹⁵ They are almost all broken into pieces and those in worship thickly greased with red ochre paste (*sindūr*), which often makes it difficult to get a sense of their chronology, dimensions or physical context. The more discernible fragments at Bhuara, Barod, Naha and Siyari bear close comparison to those at Sunari (**fig. 21, map 3**). Their size suggests they were part of monumental images, ranging in height from 1.5 metres to as much as 3 metres in the case of Bhuara. They all have broad bases for erecting them on the ground or projecting tenons for insertion into pedestals. And as at Sunari, they present a well-modelled anatomical form, elaborately ornamented and turned to face front, a headdress with coiled tiers, and a face with bulging eyes and bared teeth, thus pointing to a standardisation of style and iconography by the 11th century. This is not without significant variations in the treatment of the protagonist's threatening features and in the portrayal of the enemy—either as a lone male warrior or paired with an emaciated female, engaged in a futile contest or already subjugated.

The ubiquity of Hanuman statuary in the hinterland compels us to contend with monumentality and seriality not only as a matter of artistic production, but also in terms of the social intervention brought about by such large, freestanding stone statues

installed in village contexts and distributed serially across the landscape. These sculptures were not installed inside a monumental shrine but stood in the open air, majestically exposed to the elements. They are sometimes stationed along an access route, on or near the raised mound of a reservoir, as we find at Khajuraho and other sites in central India,⁹⁶ which would correspond well to the present location of the Sunari fragments, on a *cabūtrā* next to the embankment of the village tank.

In all these cases, the figure of Hanuman appears in an independent capacity. There is no discernible reference to Rama himself, in whose service he performs heroic feats in the *Ramayana*, but who remains absent in the iconography as well as the placement of these statues. There is, however, a wider pattern of cultic association between Hanuman and Shiva, which has been documented in the archaeological landscape of Badoh-Pathari,⁹⁷ and was noticed at Barod in the environs of Udaypur, where a fragmentary statue lies beside the remains of a Shiva temple, in a field adjoining the village tank (**map 3, fig. 22**). This topographic relationship parallels portrayals in literary compositions, such as the *Hanumānnāṭakam*, an 11th-century dramaturgical work from the Paramara court, in which it is Hanuman's character as an avatar of Rudra, the destructive aspect of Shiva, that takes precedence over his obedient service to the self-restrained Rama.⁹⁸ If such an understanding seems influenced by the dominance of Shaivism, adherence to its precepts was secondary to Hanuman's independent cult status as the embodiment of superhuman strength and the focus of popular worship.

Ethnographers have long noted that the popularity wielded by Hanuman in village contexts has little to do with his subaltern status in the divine hierarchy. Leonard Wolcott notes that in eastern

95. These sculptures were documented during field visits to villages neighbouring Udaypur in winter 2019–2020, based on notices given in RAG 2007, pp. 57–119.

96. DESAI 1996, p. 21. For the statue still *in situ* at Indor (Guna district, M.P.), see AIIS negative no. 82.87.

97. CASILE 2014, p. 139, and CASILE 2009, III, pp. 49, 56, 82, 99, 128, 130.

98. MISHRA 1978.

Uttar Pradesh and Bihar, Hanuman is a “power-dispensing” deity, whose worship is above all “an act of appropriating his strength, which can ward off ghosts (*bhūt*), spirits of the dead (*pret*), and vicious human beings,” and on which the “life of man, the growth of grain in the fields, the produce of cattle, the strength of oxen are all dependent.”⁹⁹ Similarly, in villages of Madhya Pradesh, Ian Duncan found that the heroism of Hanuman is linked less to his deeds in the *Ramayana*, than to his supernatural powers of protecting crops from bad weather, healing diseases like smallpox, curing snake-bites, dispelling bad astrological influences and safeguarding the settlement against natural and supernatural harm.¹⁰⁰ These observations are an important indication of the kind of expectations brought to bear upon the deity, deeply rooted in immediate concerns of the here and now rather than the soteriological expectations from Vishnu or Shiva.

Yet, the persistence of Hanuman’s role as a village strongman does not fully explain the intervention of the old trampling figure and the assumptions underlying its extraordinary efficacy. Modern statues of Hanuman, often a roughly carved block of stone, still present him as the epitome of bodily strength, now bearing a mace and a mountain in his two hands, but gone are the lurking demons and the threatening gestures that once charged the image with dramatic tension.¹⁰¹ What distinguishes the mediaeval statuary is the particular set of collective resources harnessed to address and affect their historical audience in transformative ways. The body language of trampling over the enemy draws its rhetorical force from a fairly literal metaphor of triumph on the battlefield, which was widely employed in the iconography of other demon-slaying divinities to articulate spiritual and political action alike.¹⁰² Other formal characteristics rely on mythological stories of the monkey hero, who miraculously expands his body, carries mountains to the battlefield, leaps across the ocean, defeats a series of deadly demons, delivers a blow to the demoness Lankini, and burns down the great demon city of Lanka with his tail.¹⁰³ Thus, the great size of the statues, the imposing physique of the protagonist, his energetic stance with a raised hand and coiled tail are all geared to make heroic prowess manifest in its most raw, readily recognisable form as bodily strength. The vanquished demons are rarely depicted with any discernible specificity, suggesting not only a degree of artistic flexibility within a set iconographic paradigm, but also a malleability of the visual referents to different social situations—from armed conflict to disease and crop failure—so that the adversary, and indeed the champion, could assume various attitudes in the contest.

99. WOLCOTT 1978, p. 658.

100. DUNCAN 2007.

101. This subject has received some limited attention in LUTGENDORF 2007, pp. 60–61.

102. KOIJ 1994 and KOIJ 1999.

103. LUTGENDORF 2007.

Figure 22. — Torso of a Hanuman statue and a Shiva-linga preserved *in situ* at Barod. Photo: Saarthak Singh.

The affective charge of the sculptures is concentrated in the arresting gaze of the deity, whose protruding eyes, elaborated with extraordinary delicacy at Sunari, confront the viewer head-on. Unlike the compassionate glance of Vishnu, the wrathful look of Hanuman is more ambivalent because of its apotropaic address, which, together with the threatening gestures and trampling stance, appears to ward off rather than welcome.¹⁰⁴ But given the belief that visual interaction between deity and worshipper is beneficial and protective, the rhetoric of the potentially harmful glance, as clarified by Lawrence Babb, operates through an inner logic of envy and submission.¹⁰⁵ Thus, if Hanuman’s raw expression of power over the adversary can prove harmful to the envious regard of ill-disposed elements, this outward wrath can also be rendered harmless to the regard of devotional deference, becoming instead a valuable attitude to be appropriated. In the transformative exchange, the physical act of touching or falling at Hanuman’s feet—especially as they trample over demonic forces—activates the extrusive flow of his special powers, for the very gesture of submission invokes a reciprocal obligation on the deity’s protection.¹⁰⁶ Thus, by eliciting participation through its visible capacity for violence the image of Hanuman brought about a forceful intervention in its local context, especially as freestanding monumental statuary anchored in the agrarian landscape and situated within a coherent system of social expectations.

104. LINROTHE 1999, pp. 12–14, 19–25 offers a useful discussion on the theme of wrathful deities, although it is based on images in an esoteric Buddhist context.

105. BABB 1981, p. 394, suggests that this assumption is rooted in the projection of worshippers’ own envy of the gods, who in turn are seen to jealously guard their supremacy over men, so that “submission is the obvious antidote.”

106. BABB 1981, p. 395.

Conclusion

The foregoing analysis of sculptures from Sunari constitutes concrete evidence for the existence of a local workshop of master artists in eastern Malwa during the 11th century. We have sought to define this locale of artistic production and its period of activity based on multiple statues of the same iconographic type, size and structural format, each designed to be an independent focus of devotion. The corpus is unified by stylistic characteristics that are part of broader trends yet peculiar to this group of sculptures.

Our analysis of the Sunari workshop has broader implications for prevailing understandings of artistic production in central India during the post-10th centuries. In this age of hectic temple building, monumentality as a phenomenon gained greater visibility in architecture, but the idea was also elaborated in sculpture in significant ways. We have demonstrated how the freestanding statues of Sunari, through their large size, variations of scale in multi-figure compositions, imposing attitudes and micro-architectural references, assume some of the formal and conceptual qualities of monumental temples that came to increasingly dominate the landscape. The patronage of large temples in great numbers in central India transformed sculptural production significantly, so much so that scholars have invoked the precedence of 'quantity over quality' in characterising figural sculpture as profusely ornate, stereotyped and even perfunctory.¹⁰⁷ However, the Sunari corpus calls for a more positive assessment of figural stone carving during this period, as they register a shift in aesthetic priorities away from the individuality of details towards their accumulated totality, often resulting in a greater complexity of form and meaning.

Standardisation of imagery was not only a practical way of dealing with increased demand, illustrated by the modular production of temple statuary, but also had meaningful implications, as in the serried sequences of deities turning the Boar's body into a crowded microcosm. The seriality of sculpture lent coherence within larger spatial paradigms, reconciling the vitality of local idioms like that of Sunari to the evolving regional styles that took shape under dynastic patronage at Udaypur. The rural *cabūtrā* assemblages from Sunari and other sites in the hinterland of Udaypur draw attention to their prolific artistic

production, not only in the abundance of sculptural remains from the 11th–12th centuries but also the stylistic relationships they reveal between works found at different sites. The intervention brought about by workshops for stone sculpture is brought into sharp relief by the Hanuman statues distributed across the rural countryside, which surpass the high gods of temple Hinduism in their size, dynamism and popularity. As such, we are compelled to rethink the 'local,' not as a discrete, isolated unit of analysis but as part of a network of several locales, in dialogue with production at centres of royal patronage.

Sculptural assemblages at villages such as Sunari are also of relevance to the religious history of a period said to be dominated by Shaivism.¹⁰⁸ The architectural and urban outcome of Shaiva ascendance is well attested at Udaypur by the establishment of a planned town, centred upon a grand Shiva temple and surrounded by a tank, built under the patronage of the Paramara king Udayaditya.¹⁰⁹ Notwithstanding this royal preference for Shaivism marked by the building of towering temples, the humbler religious landscape of little-known localities in the hinterland of monumental urban centres shows the continuing popularity of devotion to Vishnu alongside other deities, both Shaiva and non-Shaiva. The picture of a dominant Shaivism at Udaypur is considerably nuanced by an inscription from Amera, 1.5 kilometres to the south, recording the foundation of a water reservoir in 1094 CE (*vikrama* 1151) with the blessings of Vishnu and his conch,¹¹⁰ as well as by the abundance of Vishnu statues in surrounding villages and in neighbouring temple towns.¹¹¹ That sculptures of both Vaishnava and Shaiva deities were designed using the same modular structure shows that there was no abrupt change in artistic practice with the royal patronage of Shaivism at Udaypur, even if that may have prompted a qualitative and quantitative shift in the large-scale production of monumental statuary in the countryside.

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107. STADTNER & WILLIS 1996, p. 497 and PARIMOO 2000, p. 340.

108. SANDERSON 2009.

109. See note 16 above.

110. TRIVEDI H.V. 1978, p. 100, lines 1–5, verses 1–2.

111. Remains of several monumental statues of Vishnu at Badoh-Pathari, dateable to 10th–11th centuries, are stored in the reserve collection of the site museum, and discussed in CASILE 2009, III, pp. 160–164.

Bibliography

- AGRAWALA Vasudeva S., 1963: *Solar Symbolism of the Boar: Yajña-Varāha, An Interpretation*, Varanasi, Devkumar, Prithivi Prakashan.
- AIIS: *American Institute of Indian Studies, photographic archives*, Gurgaon.
- ANSARI Muzaffar Ahmed, 2012: "Muratpur and the Udaypur Praśasti: New Discoveries," *Journal of the Royal Asiatic Society*, 22 (1), pp. 29–33.
- ARIE 1964–1965: *Annual Reports on Indian Epigraphy (1964-65)*, New Delhi, Archaeological Survey of India.
- 1981–1982: *Annual Reports on Indian Epigraphy for 1981-82*, New Delhi, Archaeological Survey of India.
- 1982–1983: *Annual Reports on Indian Epigraphy for 1982-83*, New Delhi, Archaeological Survey of India.
- ASHER Frederick M., 1983: "Historical and Political Allegory in Gupta Art," in SMITH Bardwell (ed.), *Essays on Gupta Culture*, New Delhi, Motilal Banarasidas, pp. 53–65.
- 1998: "Stone and the Production of Images," *East and West*, 48 (3/4), pp. 313–328.
- ATHERTON Cynthia Packert, 1996: "Hinglajgarh," in TURNER Jane (ed.), *The Dictionary of Art*, vol. 14, London, Macmillan Publishers, p. 563.
- BABB Lawrence A., 1981: "Glancing: Visual Interaction in Hinduism," *Journal of Anthropological Research*, 37 (4), pp. 387–401.
- BAKKER Hans Teye, 2019: "At the Right Side of the Teacher: Imagination, imagery, and image in Vedic and Śaiva initiation," in BAKKER H.T., *Holy Ground: Where Art and Text Meet*, Leiden, E.J. Brill, pp. 505–526.
- BECKER Catherine, 2010: "Not Your Average Boar: The Colossal Varāha at Erān, an Iconographic Innovation," *Artibus Asiae*, 70 (1), pp. 123–149.
- BEGLAR J.D., 1878: *Report of a Tour in Bundelkhand and Malwa, 1871-72 and in the Central Provinces, 1873-74*, Archaeological Survey of India, vol. 7, Calcutta, Superintendent of Government Printing.
- BRANCACCIO Pia, 2011: *The Buddhist Caves at Aurangabad: Transformations in Art and Religion*, Leiden, E.J. Brill.
- 2018: "Monumentality, Nature and World Heritage monuments: The Rock-Cut Sites of Ajanta, Ellora and Elephanta in Maharashtra," in RAY Himanshu Prabha (ed.), *Decolonising Heritage in South Asia: The Global, the National and the Transnational*, London, Routledge, pp. 111–128.
- BRUHN Klaus, 1969: *The Jina-Images of Deogarh*, Leiden, E.J. Brill.
- BUCCELLATI Federico, HAGENEUER Sebastian, VAN DER HEYDEN Sylva & LEVENSON Felix (eds.), 2019: *Size Matters—Understanding Monumentality across Ancient Civilizations*, [e-book], transcript Verlag.
- CASILE Anne, 2009: "Temples et expansion d'un centre religieux en Inde centrale. Lectures du paysage archéologique de Badoh-Pathāri du 5e au 10e siècle de notre ère," 3 vols., PhD dissertation, Paris, Paris 3, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.891427>.
- 2014: "Vadovyapattana: An Agro-urban Centre and its Hinterland in Paramara Times," in WILLIS Michael D., RAG Pankaj & MISRA O.P. (eds.), *Patrimoine culturel de l'eau: Cities and Settlements, Temples and Tanks in the Medieval Landscape of Central India*, Bhopal, Directorate of Archaeology, Archives and Museums, Madhya Pradesh, pp. 133–155.
- CECIL Elizabeth A. & BISSCHOP Peter C., 2021: "Idiom and Innovation in the 'Gupta Period': Revisiting Eran and Sondhni," *The Indian Economic and Social History Review*, 58 (1), pp. 29–71.
- CHAKRAVARTY Kalyan Kumar, 1984: *Gwalior Fort: Art, Culture and History*, New Delhi, Arnold-Heinemann.
- CUNNINGHAM Alexander, 1871: *Archaeological Survey of India: Four Reports Made During the Years 1862-63-64-65*, 2 vols., Simla, Government Central Press.
- 1880: *Tour in Bundelkhand and Malwa in 1874-75 and 1876-77*, Archaeological Survey of India Report, vol. 10, Calcutta, Superintendent of Government Printing.
- DEHEJIA Vidya & ROCKWELL Peter, 2016: *The Unfinished: The Stone Carvers at Work in the Indian*, New Delhi, Roli.
- DESAI Devangana, 1996: *The Religious Imagery of Khajuraho*, Mumbai, Franco-Indian Research.
- DEVA Krishna, 1975: "Bhūmija Temples," in CHANDRA Pramod (ed.), *Studies in Indian Temple Architecture*, New Delhi, American Institute of Indian Studies, pp. 90–113.
- 1990: *Temples of Khajuraho*, 2 vols., Delhi, Archaeological Survey of India.
- DHAKY Madhusudan A., 1977: *The Indian Temple Forms in Karṇāṭa Inscriptions and Architecture*, New Delhi, Abhinav Publications.
- DIKSHIT S.K., 1962: *A Guide to the Central Archaeological Museum, Gwalior*, Bhopal, Department of Archaeology and Museums, Government of Madhya Pradesh.
- DUNCAN Ian, 2007: "Hanumān Mahāvīrasvāmī: The Mountain Hero in a Plains Village," in BRÜCKNER Heidrun, VAN SKYHAWK Hugh & ZOLLER Claus Peter (eds.), *The Concept of the Hero in Indian Culture*, New Delhi, Manohar Publishers & Distributors, pp. 41–59.
- DWIVEDI S.K., 1991: *Temple Sculptures of India: With Special Reference to the Sculptures of the Bhumija Temples of Malwa*, Delhi, Agam Kala Prakashan.
- FLEET John Faithful, 1888: "Eran Stone Boar Inscription of Toramāṇa," in FLEET J.F., *Inscriptions of the Early Gupta Kings and their Successors*, Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum, vol. 3, Calcutta, Superintendent of Government Printing.
- FLOOD Finbarr Barry, 2015: "Idea and Idiom: Knowledge as Praxis in South Asian and Islamic Architecture," *Ars Orientalis*, 45, pp. 148–162.
- GARDE M.B., 1924: *Annual Report of the Archaeological Department, Gwalior State, for Samvat 1980/Year 1923-24*, Gwalior, Alijah Darbar Press.
- GOLDMAN Robert & GOLDMAN Sally Sutherland, 1996: *Rāmāyaṇa: Book Five, Sundara by Vālmiki*, Princeton, N.J., Princeton University Press.
- GRANOFF Phyllis, 1997: "Heaven on Earth: Temples and Temple Cities of Medieval India," in VAN DER MEIJ Dick (ed.), *India and Beyond: Aspects of Literature, Meaning, Ritual and Thought; Essays in honour of Frits Staal*, London–New York, Kegan Paul International, pp. 170–193.
- HARDY Adam, 2014: "Bhoja, Bhojpur and the Bhumija," in WILLIS Michael D., RAG Pankaj & MISRA O.P. (eds.), *Patrimoine culturel de l'eau: Cities and Settlements, Temples and Tanks in the Medieval Landscape of Central India*, Bhopal, Directorate of Archaeology, Archives and Museums, Madhya Pradesh, pp. 35–55.
- 2015: *Theory and Practice of Temple Architecture in Medieval India: Bhoja's Samarāṅgaṇasūtradhāra and the Bhojpur Line Drawings*, New Delhi, Indira Gandhi National Centre for the Arts, Dev Publishers & Distributors.
- JHA Vishwa Mohan, 2008: "Economy of North India," in SHARMA R.S. & SHRIMALI K.M. (eds.), *Comprehensive History of India*, vol. 4, pt. 2, Delhi, Manohar, pp. 261–310.
- JOSHI N.P., 1981: "Regional trends in some of the medieval Brahmanical sculptures of Malwa," in KHARE M.D. (ed.), *Malwa through the Ages (papers of the seminar held at Indore Museum on 7, 8 and 9 February, 1981)*, Bhopal, Archaeology & Museums Madhya Pradesh, pp. 106–117.
- VAN KOOIJ Karel R., 1994: "Iconography of the battlefield: Narasimha and Durgā," in *South Asian Archaeology 1993*, Helsinki, Suomalainen Tiedekatemia, vol. 1, pp. 378–386.
- 1999: "Iconography of the Battlefield: The Case of Chinnamastā," in HOUBEN J.E.M. & VAN KOOIJ K.R. (eds.), *Violence Denied: Violence, Non-Violence and the Rationalization of Violence in South Asian Cultural History*, Leiden, E.J. Brill, pp. 249–294.
- KRAMRISCH Stella, 1933: *Indian Sculpture*, Calcutta, YMCA Publishing House.
- LAMBOURN Elizabeth, 2004: "Carving and Communities: Marble Carving for Muslim Patrons at Khambhāt and around the Indian Ocean Rim, Late Thirteenth–Mid-Fifteenth Centuries," *Ars Orientalis*, 34, pp. 99–133.
- LASCARIDES-ZANNAS Elik, 1981: "The Big Śukanāsa of Udayeśvara Temple at Udayapur, Madhya Pradesh," in NAGARAJA RAO M.S. (ed.), *Madhu: Recent Researches in Indian Archaeology and Art History: Shri M.N. Deshpande Festschrift*, Delhi, Agam Kala Prakashan, pp. 187–194.
- LEDDEROSE Lothar, 2000: *Ten Thousand Things: Module and Mass Production in Chinese Art*, Princeton, Princeton University Press.
- LEVILLAIN Johan, 2021: "Donner corps à l'Inde médiévale. Les formes féminines dans la sculpture paramāra au XI^e siècle," *Bulletin de l'École française d'Extrême-Orient*, 107, pp. 87–135.
- LINROTHE Robert, 1999: *Ruthless Compassion: Wrathful Deities in Early Indo-Tibetan Esoteric Buddhist Art*, Boston, Shambhala.
- LORENZETTI Tiziana, 2000: *A Guide to the Appreciation of the Indian Sculptures in the Archaeological Museum of Khajuraho*, Calcutta–Delhi, Indica Books.

- LUTGENDORF Phillip, 2007: *Hanuman's Tail: The Messages of a Divine Monkey*, Oxford, Oxford University Press.
- MASON Darielle, 1993: "A Sense of Time and Place: Style and Architectural Disposition of Images on the North Indian Temple," in MASON Darielle & DESAI Vishakha (eds.), *Gods, Guardians, and Lovers: Temple Sculptures from North India, A.D. 700-1200*, New York, Asia Society / Seattle, University of Washington Press, pp. 116-138.
- MEISTER Michael W., 1982: "Bīṭhū: Individuality and Idiom," *Ars Orientalis*, 13, pp. 169-186.
- 1983: "The Udayeśvara Temple Plan," in RAMAN K.V. (ed.), *Srinidhih: Perspectives in Indian Archaeology, Art and Culture*, Shri K. R. Srinivasan Festschrift, Madras, New Era Publications, pp. 85-93.
- 1986: "On the Development of a Morphology for a Symbolic Architecture: India," *RES: Anthropology and Aesthetics*, 12, pp. 33-50.
- 1993: "Style and Idiom in the Art of Uparamala," *Muqarnas*, 10, pp. 344-354
- MEISTER Michael W. & DHAKY M.A. (eds.), 1988-1991: *Encyclopaedia of Indian Temple Architecture*, Delhi, American Institute of Indian Studies, Oxford University Press. Vol. 2, part 1, *North India, Foundations of North Indian Style, c. 250 B.C.-A.D. 1100* (1988); vol. 2, part 2: *North India, Period of Early Maturity, c. A.D. 700-900* (1991).
- MISHRA Damodara (ed.), 1978: *Hanumannāṭakam*, tr. Jagadish Mishra, Varanasi, Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office.
- MISRA R.N., 2009: *Śilpa in Indian Tradition: Concept and Instrumentalities*, Shimla, Indian Institute of Advanced Studies / New Delhi, Aryan Books International.
- MITTAL Amarchand, 1979: *The Inscriptions of Imperial Paramāras*, Ahmedabad, L.D. Institute of Indology.
- MOSTELLER John F., 1987: "A New Approach for the Study of Indian Art," *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 107 (1), pp. 55-69.
- 1988a: "Texts and Craftsmen at Work," in MEISTER Michael W. (ed.), *Making Things in South Asia: The Role of Artist and Craftsman*, Philadelphia, Department of South Asia Regional Studies, pp. 24-33.
- 1988b: "The Study of Indian Iconometry in Historical Perspective," *Journal of the American Oriental Society*, 108 (1), pp. 99-110.
- MUKHERJI Purno Chander, 1899: *Report on the Antiquities in the District of Lalitpur, N.-W. Provinces, India*, Roorkee, Thomason Engineering College Press.
- NANAVATI J.M. & DHAKY Madhusudan A., 1963: *The Ceilings in the Temples of Gujarat*, Baroda, Museum and Picture Gallery.
- PANDE Anupa, 2018: *The Udayeśvara Temple: Art, Architecture and Philosophy of the Śaiva Siddhānta*, New Delhi, Aryan Books International.
- PANDEY Shyam Manohar, 1993-1994: "Surasā, Simhikā and Laṅkā in the Vālmīki and other Rāmāyaṇas," *Indologica Taurinensia*, 19-20, pp. 227-244.
- PARIMOO Ratan, 2000: "The Formation of Medieval Style in Malwa Region (A Presentation of Hinglajgarh Sculptures)," in PARIMOO Ratan, *Studies in Indian Sculpture (Regional Genres and Interpretations)*, Essays in New Art History, vol. 1, New Delhi, Books & Books, pp. 320-343.
- PRASAD Maheshwari, 1989: *Some Aspects of the Varāha-Kathā in Epics and Puranas*, Delhi, Pratibha Prakashan.
- RAG Pankaj (ed.), 2007: *Vidiśā jile kā purātattva (grāmāvār sarveśāna par ādhārit)*, Bhopal, Directorate of Archaeology, Archives and Museums, Madhya Pradesh.
- RANGARAJAN HariPriya, 1997: *Varāha Images in Madhya Pradesh: An Iconographic Study*, Mumbai, Somaiya Publications.
- 2015: "Unique iconographic feature of Yajna-Varaha from Badoh Pathari (Madhya Pradesh)," in BANERJI Arundhati (ed.), *Ratnasri: Gleanings from Indian Archaeology, Art History and Indology*, New Delhi, Kaveri Books, pp. 93-101.
- RENNER Zsuzsanna, 2012: "Viṣṇu Varāha (Vadkan) avatārāja az indiai szövegekben és művészetben," PhD dissertation, Budapest, Eötvös Loránd University.
- ROCKWELL Peter, 1993: *The Art of Stoneworking: A Reference Guide*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- SANDERSON Alexis, 2009: "The Śaiva Age: The Rise and Dominance of Śaivism during the Early Medieval Period," in EINOO Shingo (ed.), *Genesis and Development of Tantrism*, Tokyo, Institute of Oriental Culture, University of Tokyo, pp. 41-349.
- SEARS Tamara I., 2015: "Following River Routes and Artistic Transmissions in Medieval Central India," *Ars Orientalis*, 45, pp. 43-77.
- SHARMA R.K., 1998: *Encyclopaedia of Art, Archaeology, and Literature in Central India*, Delhi, Aryan Books International.
- SINGH Veerendra, 2017: "Sunāri meṁ viṣṇu ke 24 rūpoṁ kā saṁket," *Patrikā*, 10 February 2017, <https://www.patrika.com/vidisha-news/vishnu-s-24-forms-indicating-goldsmithy-1506857/>.
- SINGH Saarthak, 2019: "Foundation record of the Udayeśvara temple at Udaypur, Madhya Pradesh, dated year 1137," *Siddham: The Asian Inscriptions Database*, <https://siddham.network/inscription/inpar1501/>.
- 2020: "Hanuman statue inscription from Sunari," *Zenodo*, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6867657>.
- SINHA Ajay J., 2000: *Imagining Architects: Creativity in the Religious Monuments of India*, Newark, Delaware, University of Delaware Press.
- STADTNER Donald M. & WILLIS Michael D., 1996: "Sculpture: Central, 10th-13th centuries," in TURNER Jane (ed.), *The Dictionary of Art*, vol. 15, London, Macmillan Publishers, pp. 496-497.
- SURESH K.M., 1999: *Iconography of Vishnu from Khajuraho*, Delhi, Bharatiya Kala Prakashan.
- TICHT Doria, 2010: "The Udayeśvara Temple, Udayapur: Architecture and Iconography of an 11th Century Temple in Central India," PhD dissertation, Cardiff University.
- 2012: "Le programme iconographique du temple d'Udayeśvara à Udayapur, Madhya Pradesh, xi^e siècle," *Arts Asiatiques*, 67, pp. 3-18.
- 2014: "A Royal Temple: The Udayeśvara Temple at Udaypur," in WILLIS Michael D., RAG Pankaj & MISRA O.P. (eds.), *Patrimoine culturel de l'eau: Cities and Settlements, Temples and Tanks in the Medieval Landscape of Central India*, Bhopal, Directorate of Archaeology, Archives and Museums, Madhya Pradesh.
- TRIVEDI Harihar Vitthal, 1978: *Inscriptions of the Paramāras, Chandēllas, Kachchapaghātas and two minor dynasties*, Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum, vol. 7, part 2, New Delhi, Archaeological Survey of India.
- 1989: *Inscriptions of the Paramāras, Chandēllas, Kachchapaghātas and two minor dynasties*, Corpus Inscriptionum Indicarum, vol. 7, part 3, New Delhi, Archaeological Survey of India.
- TRIVEDI P.K., 1995: *Art Traditions of the Paramāras of Vāgaḍa*, Jaipur, Publication Scheme.
- TRIVEDI R.D., 1990: *Temples of the Pratihāra period in Central India*, New Delhi, Archaeological Survey of India.
- WILLIS Michael D., 1988: "An Introduction to the Historical Geography of Gopakṣetra, Daśārṇa, and Jejākadeśa," *Bulletin of the School of Oriental and African Studies*, 51 (2), pp. 271-278.
- 2009: *The Archaeology of Hindu Ritual: Temples and the Establishment of Gods*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press.
- WOLCOTT Leonard, 1978: "Hanumān: The Power-dispensing Monkey in North Indian Folk Religion," *Journal of Asian Studies*, 37, pp. 653-661.